

Data-efficient Domain Transfer for Instance Segmentation for AR Scenes

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Abstract—Augmented Reality (AR) applications rely heavily on the accurate detection and segmentation of objects in order to seamlessly integrate virtual content into real world environments. However, achieving robust object detection and segmentation in AR scenes remains challenging, in particular when specific classes need to be covered. Due to the lack of sufficient real annotated data, training can rely on synthetic data, which has the issue of the domain gap between synthetic and real-world images. This paper addresses the challenge of generalisation in object detection/instance segmentation models trained with synthetic data. It presents techniques to improve the generalisation capability of object detection models trained on synthetic data for real-world applications. Our method is based on the model soup approach, where models trained with different data subsets and hyperparameters are combined to achieve better generalisation performance. The experimental results on the validation dataset of the ADAPT sim2real Object Detection Challenge 2023 demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach in achieving good generalisation performance. This marks a significant step towards more reliable and adaptable object detection and segmentation approaches for AR applications.

Index Terms—Instance Segmentation, Domain Shift, Model Soup, ADAPT Sim2Real Challenge

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital Twin and Extended Reality (XR) applications often address very specific application scenarios, for example, in industrial applications. The objects of interest encountered in these scenarios – e.g. machinery, equipment, parts, final products – are likely not present in everyday scenes, and may require very fine-grained classification. Thus the widely used object detection and segmentation datasets as well as the models trained on them will not support these objects. The only alternative is thus to train (or at least fine-tune) a custom model to support these classes of objects. If a sufficient number of real images is available at all, it may be difficult to obtain annotations for a set of images large and diverse enough for training.

Training on synthetic, i.e. computer rendered, images has the advantage of generating large datasets at low costs, as the annotations for the particular task (e.g., segmentation masks) can be created together with the photorealistic images. However, the main challenges are to create datasets that also reflect

the types of background and clutter that will occur in the target environment, and in general, to bridge the appearance gap from clear rendered images to real images that include various types of noise from the environment and the capture pipeline. Next to many other approaches for bridging this domain gap, improving the generalisation of the model with using no or little data from the target domain is an approach requiring little extra training effort and data. Fusing multiple versions of a model, which are obtained from different checkpoints, training with different hyperparameters or subsets of the data, has been shown to improve these process.

Our main contributions are:

- We propose a dataset creation pipeline for rendering images and ground truth, focusing on segmenting untextured and hard to discriminate objects in complex environments. The resulting images are provided as a public dataset.
- To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work to adopt the idea of manifold mixing model soup [1] for fusing the weights of multiple fine-tuned models to the problem of instance segmentation.
- Using data from a challenge focusing on industrial use cases, we validate different variants of applying the proposed approach.

The rest of this paper is organised as follows. We introduce the challenge from which we use the source models and real validation images in Section I-A. Section II reviews related work on instance segmentation and fusion of multiple trained models. In Section III we introduce the dataset generation pipeline, describe the experiments and results in Section IV and conclude the paper with Section V.

A. The ADAPT sim2real Object Detection Challenge 2023

Object detection is a crucial capability for industrial robotic systems. Therefore, being able to train object detection algorithms using CAD models can significantly enhance the flexibility of these systems. This objective was addressed through the ADvanced Agile ProductiOn (ADAPT) sim2real Object Detection Challenge 2023, run by the METRICS project¹.

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¹“Metrological Evaluation and Testing of Robots in International Competitions,” <https://metricsproject.eu/>

Participants were provided with 12 CAD models of assembly parts to generate synthetic training images using rendering tools. During testing, a real validation set comprising 777 images (referred to as *sim2realR* dataset), each annotated with ground truth labels, was provided to compute the accuracy and efficacy of the detection algorithms that were trained under the constraint of limited access to real data. The evaluation criterion used is mean average precision at 50 (mAP50), which means that an IoU threshold of 0.5 was used to obtain the true positive detections.

II. RELATED WORK

We review related work on instance segmentation approaches, as well as approaches for improving generalisation capabilities in domain adaption by fusing multiple models.

A. Instance Segmentation

BEiT [2] adopts the successful approach of BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) from natural language processing, using 16×16 image patches as visual tokens. The model is pretrained by masking patches and then fine-tuned to specific downstream tasks such as semantic segmentation and instance segmentation. InternImage [3] is a vision foundation model, which – in contrast to most other recent foundation models – is not based on transformers but a CNN architecture, proposing an adaptation of deformable convolutions tailored for foundation models. ConvNeXt [4] follows a similar approach, i.e. adopting concepts from vision transformers that can be implemented with the building blocks of a convolutional architecture, thus achieving less complex models performing comparably with transformers. Swin transformer [5] is a backbone for vision tasks, adding the concept of shifted windows in the attention block, implemented as an hierarchical architecture. The backbone serves a number of downstream tasks, including semantic and instance segmentation. MaskDino [6] is based on the DETR [7] transformer-based object detector, and its improved version DINO [8] adds a mask detection branch to this architecture. OneFormer [9] is a transformer-based model aiming to unify semantic segmentation, instance segmentation and panoptic segmentation with a shared backbone. Mask2Former [10] addresses a similar aim of addressing different segmentation tasks with one architecture, which in this case introduces a transformer decoder with masked attention. Recently, approaches based on vision-language foundation models have been proposed, e.g. SAM [11]. However, in a scenario with very specific objects of interest, these models are likely not to have the knowledge about their appearance encoded, so that the few- and zero-shot capabilities of these models cannot be exploited. In addition, these approaches are still computationally considerably more expensive than vision-only based methods.

B. Merging models for domain adaptation

To address the domain shift problem, the so-called Sim2Real gap [12], several approaches have been proposed. One method [13] involves directly minimising the domain

Fig. 1. The 12 CAD models with relevant poses.

gap by distilling general “objectness” knowledge learned from a model such as SAM. Another strategy uses Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), such as StyleGAN, to create style-mixed images that closely mimic real-world images, such as in [14].

A variety of methods has been proposed recently for merging several models into one fused model, with the aim of increasing the generalisation capability and robustness to distribution shifts of the fused model. Stochastic weight averaging (SWA) [15] produces the fused model by averaging the weights of a set of models sampled from the final stages of a single training run. Different approaches for training an ensemble of models in parallel in the final stage of model training and averaging the obtained weights have been proposed [16], [17]. The work of [18] shows that averaging the weights of multiple models fine-tuned with different hyperparameter configurations often improves accuracy and out-of-distribution performance of the averaged model. They propose two different averaging algorithms (which they call “souping”), *uniform soup* and *greedy soup*. The uniform soup is a very simple procedure, as it does an averaging of all fine-tuned models. In contrast, the greedy soup is constructed by sequentially adding each model as a potential ingredient to the soup, and only keeping the model if it improves the performance of the averaged model. The authors of [19] found that while fine-tuning a pretrained vision model improves performance on the downstream task, it also tends to decrease accuracy on the original pretraining task. They therefore propose a robust finetuning procedure called *WiSE-FT* that computes a weighted average of the original pretrained parameters and the fine-tuned parameters. Different weighting values produce different trade-offs between pretraining and finetuning task performance.

So far, the model soup approach has mostly been applied

TABLE I
12 OBJECT CLASSES

ID	Object				
1	Top Casing	5	Cover	9	Button
2	Gear	6	Housing	10	Cam
3	Bottom Casing	7	Planet	11	Case End
4	Carrier	8	Sun	12	Case Middle

to classification, but there is little work on segmentation. For visual domain adaptation in waste sorting, Kim et al. [20] propose averaging models trained with different sets of pseudo-labels. Recently, Wasfy et al. [21] showed that mixing different checkpoints from training a LiDAR segmentation model provides improvements. However, more advanced weighting and mixing schemes as proposed in [1] have not yet been explored for segmentation.

III. DATASET CREATION

In order to create a synthetic dataset covering the 12 object classes (listed in Table I) we used the following workflow, inspired by [22], leveraging NVIDIA’s OptiX raytracing engine [23]:

- Conversion of 12 initial 3D models to a suitable format (from .ply format to .obj using the *Open3d* Python package).
- Preprocessing the 3D objects to generate poses that can be easily positioned in a virtual environment (see Fig. 1), by shifting the centre point towards the bottom of the object.
- Creating a virtual scenery with a textured table plane to place objects on.
- Set up materials, textures, lights, cameras and camera paths in OptiX (see Fig. 2).
- Adding algorithms for object placement, camera rotation, light positioning and texture variance.
- Using GPU-accelerated ray tracing to create image pairs of realistic and masked images (see Fig. 3). The mask image is generated in a subsequent run, without table plane and all object textures set to monochrome black.
- For all selected image pairs (realistic + mask), generating a dataset description in MS COCO format.
- Collection of statistics on pixel occurrences to improve the ML training process. Data contains the minimum pixel area of an object class, the maximum area, and average, and the sum of all pixels of an object class in the whole generated dataset.

Raytracing has been done using the PlotOptiX python package v0.17.1 [24]. We have used 4 camera orbits at different radius and increasing height, with sinusoidal up/down variation. For camera settings, see table in Fig. 2.

To avoid overfitting, we randomly selected combinations of objects to put on the table. The combinations of objects increased from a single object up to seven objects placed in a hexagonal shape and in the centre.

property	turn0	turn1	turn2	turn3
type	DoF	Pinhole	Fisheye	Pinhole
positions_per_turn	75	75	75	75
eye_radius	150	250	130	50
base_height	450	550	700	750
height_variation	40	40	40	40
height_frequency	5	7	11	13
start_angle_offset	0	5	10	15

Fig. 2. Camera positions and possible object locations (top) and camera settings (bottom).

To keep things simple, the placement algorithm prevents object occlusion of any object. In addition, the texture of the table and the colours of the lights have been changed after each image. Background images were synthetically generated as blurred Perlin noise (with Python packages *perlin-noise* and *pillow*), additionally, a randomly sampled set of real images from the ADE20K dataset [25] has been used to increase variability of the background. 40K images have been generated, serving as a pool for fine-tuned selection of the training process, as not all of them were useful because they were too blurred or partially outside the image boundaries. For our experiments, the synthetic dataset was split so that 80% is used for training and the remaining 20% used for validation. These datasets are referred to as the sim2realS training and validation datasets, respectively.

The dataset is provided at <https://github.com/didymosxr/sim2real>.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

In this section, we discuss the experiments conducted for the ADAPT sim2real Object Detection Challenge 2023 and the subsequent improvements to address the domain shift by implementing strategies to improve model performance with real-world data.

Fig. 3. Seven objects with applied masks placed on the table.

Fig. 4. Comparison of evaluation results across 12 classes of the five best performing models.

A. Results of Training on Synthetic Data

An instance segmentation algorithm using a Swin backbone [5] architecture (SWIN-L) was trained on the synthetic dataset to optimise performance metrics. Models were evaluated based on their effectiveness in delineating segmented regions, and the best performing model on the sim2realR validation set was selected for submission. Fig. 4 shows the results obtained by the five best performing models during training, based on the sim2realR validation dataset, in descending order. The best model of these was submitted and we received a score of 0.52 on the challenge test dataset. The annotations of the test dataset were not made public during the challenge, so the evaluation couldn’t be done by us, but by the organisers of the challenge, using the metric of the mean average precision at 50% (mAP50).

We validated the model on a synthetic validation dataset and achieved an almost perfect recognition rate: for the mAP50 metric the overall average performance is 1.00. When using mAP, the values of all per-class scores are in the range [0.85, 1.00]. It should be noted, that the COCO mAP is calculated by averaging over 10 IoU thresholds ranging from 0.5 to 0.95 in 0.05 increments.

In addition, a comprehensive class-wise evaluation revealed significant differences in performance between the different classes, as shown in Fig. 4: While certain classes, such as Planet and Cover, showed consistent performance across models, others, such as Bottom Casing and Case Middle, showed significant differences in performance between models. Consequently, combining models and refining their generalisation capabilities by exploiting their individual strengths could potentially improve performance on a per-class basis.

These observations encouraged us to further investigate domain adaptation techniques and class-specific optimisation.

B. Enhancing Performance Across Domains

In our experiments, we adopted the manifold mixing model soup approach from [1] as a strategy to enhance our model’s generalisation, specifically targeting the domain shift from synthetic to real data. The model soup methodology revolves around the merging of multiple pretrained models into a unified model using the manifold mixing model soup algorithm. To tailor this approach to our specific needs, we took several steps. We refined our dataset to address imbalance and unusual object instances. We varied and optimised the model’s hyperparameters and incorporated class weights to better suit real-world scenes. Consequently, we selected 11 models as the basis for the model soup algorithm. The per-class results of these models are compared in Fig. 5, with Model_1 being the submitted model for the challenge.

As proposed in [19], we tested both, *uniform* and *greedy* soup methods, adapting them for instance segmentation. We divided the SWIN-L model into 13 components: 6 for the backbone, 2 for the neck, 2 for the ROI head and 3 for the RPN head. For the uniform soup, we averaged the weights of these components to create the mixed model. For the *greedy* soup we randomly selected a 5% subset of the sim2realR dataset (referred to as sim2realR5p) and sequentially added models based on their performance improvement on this subset. Models were ranked by their performance on the synthetic validation set, and details about the algorithm are in [1]. However, we optimised the mixing factor based on real images of the target domain rather than synthetic images to bridge the domain gap.

To reduce the dependency on the selected subset, the process was repeated three times, and the results of the merged models were averaged for comparison. Our initial results indicate that the combined model created through the model soup approach, by averaging individual models, has been successful. Fig. 5 presents the comparative results, highlighting the performance of the mixed model against the 11 individual models considered for mixing. This comparison shows how our adapted approach can mitigate domain shift and improve model generalisation across different domain datasets. Consequently, we observed that stochastic weight averaging (SWA) led to a better generalisation of the fused model, as noted in [1].

The observed variability in the performance of each fine-tuned model across different classes highlights the complexity associated with optimising models for instance segmentation

Comparison class-wise Results of all Model Soup Ingredients and the Mixed Model

Fig. 5. Comparison of evaluation results across 12 classes of all models contributing to the mixed model and the mixed model, obtained by averaging model components.

Improved Model Generalisation

Fig. 6. Comparison of evaluation results across 12 classes for three models: (1) best model on sim2realS validation dataset, (2) mixed model by averaging all components, and (3) mixed model with optimised mixing factors based on a subset of sim2realR validation dataset.

Fig. 7. Qualitative results: Ground Truth (left), Swin best (middle), Mixed (right).

and object classification tasks. Our analysis reveals significant variations in performance metrics across classes. Some classes exhibit consistently high performance across all fine-tuned models, whereas others display substantial performance fluctuations.

Interestingly, our results show that there are two classes where all fine-tuned models perform consistently well, suggesting inherent properties or features within these classes that facilitate effective model learning and generalisation. In contrast, the other classes exhibit high variability in performance, indicating challenges and complexities specific to these classes. Notably, the fused model achieves the best performance for 10 out of 12 classes evaluated. This suggests that merging predictions from multiple fine-tuned models effectively leverages complementary strengths and mitigates individual model weaknesses, resulting in superior overall performance.

To further enhance performance in the transferred domain, we followed the approach outlined in [1]. Using the same framework, we optimised the fusion of models on a tiny subset (again sim2realR5p) of the sim2realR validation set. This allowed us to automatically calculate the optimal mixing coefficient for each latent space manifold through an optimisation algorithm, integrating components from multiple fine-tuned models into a single model. We partitioned the model into several components (latent space manifolds) and performed optimisation to determine the optimal mixing factor for each component.

The fusion of models was carried out sequentially, iteratively mixing promising candidate models with the current fused model. We started with the best fine-tuned model as the initial fused model and progressively incorporated additional models to enhance validation accuracy. To increase the flexibility of our model selection process, we adjusted the tolerance

Fig. 8. Comparison of evaluation results across 12 classes for three models: (1) best model on sim2realS validation dataset, (2) mixed model with optimised mixing factors from sim2realR validation subset, and (3) mixed model with optimised mixing factors from sim2realR test subset.

Fig. 9. Comparison of evaluation results across 12 classes for three models: (1) model submitted for the challenge, (2) retrained and fine-tuned model on sim2realR validation dataset, and (3) mixed model with optimised mixing factors from sim2realR test subset.

factor for promising candidate models τ from 0.998 to 0.700, making the criteria for including models as soup ingredients less stringent. This adjustment proved to be particularly beneficial when using a small number of images from the target domain for optimisation, as it reduced the need for extensive annotation. Fig. 6 compares the final mixed model where an optimised mixing factor for each component was computed, with the mixed model by averaging all components and the best fine-tuned model on the sim2realS validation dataset. The optimised model shows improved generalisation over the simple averaging method, while the third model demonstrates the best generalisation performance. The results clearly show that the mixed models both successfully combine the best weights per class into a single model. The performance of 9 out of 12 classes was further improved by the optimised mixed model, with the largest improvements observed for the two worst performing classes, Planet and Sun. This approach allows us to produce a model with acceptable performance

across all classes.

Finally, Fig. 7 shows some example results. On the left are the images with the ground truth annotation. In the middle are the detection results of the best fine-tuned model, and on the right are the improved results of the mixed model. The detections are generally better, more elements could be detected and classified correctly. As evidenced by the third sample in Fig. 7, false detections were also reduced.

C. Evaluation on real test dataset

During our evaluation process, we discovered the test set and corresponding ground truth used for the challenge on Zenodo, allowing us to conduct additional experiments. Given that the test dataset is larger than the validation dataset, we randomly selected a subset of 3% of the data to optimise the mixing factors. As there is a further domain shift from the real data of the validation to the test, we were also able to improve the generalisation of the model and outperform each per-class result by the new mixed model, see Fig. 8. Due to the availability of two real datasets, we could also retrain one of the models with the real validation dataset and fine-tune the model to this real scenario with the 777 images.

Fig. 9 shows the results of the initial model compared to the fine-tuned model and the mixed model. Here we can see the limitation of our approach, the retraining results in a better model that gives better results in the specific domain than a mixed model. However, for 4 classes, the mixed model outperforms the fine-tuned model, so when no or limited training data is available, the mixed model is a good and competitive alternative to fine-tuning.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we improved the model fusion and optimisation processes by exploring innovative techniques and methodologies. This has improved the accuracy and generalisation of models trained on data resulting from a domain shift. We demonstrated the effectiveness of stochastic weight averaging (SWA) in broadening the solutions to the optimisation problem and facilitating better generalisation of fused models. Our experiments have also demonstrated the effectiveness of the manifold mixing model soup algorithm in seamlessly integrating components from multiple fine-tuned models. In addition, our research emphasises the significance of being flexible and adaptable when selecting models. We adjusted the tolerance factor τ to fit different data conditions and optimisation requirements. As a result, this reduced the strictness of model inclusion criteria and minimised the need for extensive annotation efforts. Overall, our results highlight the effectiveness of model fusion techniques in improving classification performance and mitigating the effects of class-specific variability. By combining the predictions of multiple fine-tuned models, we can achieve more robust and reliable performance across different classes, ultimately increasing the utility and applicability of our classification models in real-world scenarios.

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